

Evaluation of the Influence of Diaphragm Flexibility on the Seismic Response of Asymmetric Buildings with Slab Openings

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Abstract Diaphragm is a structural component of the building system that resists lateral forces. In general, diaphragm is considered rigid whereas in practical scenario it impacts the behaviour of the structure to a considerable extent. Therefore, there is need to study diaphragm flexibility to understand the actual behaviour of the structure. This study uses slab openings to compare rigid and flexible diaphragms with 25% and 50% flexibility in the asymmetric plan model (T and L shape). This study takes into account slab apertures between 1 and 2% at the centre and corners of the plan. Utilizing the Etabs 20 version, response spectrum analysis is done to assess seismic parameters such as inter-story drift, maximum story displacement, and story shear. Also, axial force in the column, shear force and bending moment in the beam were evaluated. The findings demonstrate how changing the flexibility alters the dynamic response. It is observed that T shape with centre opening in plan is the crucial case.

Keywords Diaphragm, Lateral force resisting system, asymmetric plan model, response spectrum analysis and slab openings.

Introduction

A horizontal structural component called a diaphragm transmits lateral force to the vertical components and preserves the structural integrity. In RCC constructions, diaphragms are typically modelled as rigid, which means there is no relative movement between the member nodes. By lowering the degree of freedom, the computational process is made easier by the assumption that there is no relative displacement in the diaphragm. The idea of a flexible diaphragm is therefore primarily taken into account in structures like unreinforced masonry buildings with wooden deck slabs, wooden sheathing in a concrete building, concrete topped metal deck, and other composite structures. However, relative displacement happens in numerous real-world instances of RCC structures, including plan asymmetric structures and structures with slab openings, where the rigid diaphragm assumption is not valid. In the instances discussed above, if rigid diaphragm assumption is used, it can lead to over estimation of the strength of the structure. A classic example to understand the importance of diaphragm flexibility is Northridge Earthquake, 1994. One of the severe damages observed in this earthquake is attributed to large Diaphragm movements causing the failure of gravity system in the parking garages. The reason for such diaphragm movement is identified to be the lack of continuity in construction joints. Therefore, to avoid potential risk, incorporating the significance of flexibility in diaphragm is needed.

Classification of diaphragm

Rigid diaphragm

When a diaphragm's midpoint displacement, under lateral load, is less than twice the average displacement at its ends, the diaphragm may be regarded as rigid. Rotational or torsional behaviour is anticipated for diaphragms that are categorised as rigid. The load is distributed among rigid diaphragms in accordance with stiffness.

Flexible diaphragm

When the midpoint displacement under lateral load exceeds twice the average displacement of the end supports, a diaphragm is said to be flexible. Torsion and rotational forces are not thought to be possible to be distributed by flexible diaphragms. The loads were divided among flexible diaphragms in accordance with the tributary area. As per IS 1893:2016, clause 7.6.4, a diaphragm is considered to be flexible if it deforms such a way that the max. lateral displacement measured from the chord of the deformed shape at any point of the diaphragm is more than 1.2 times the average displacement of the entire diaphragm.

Fig. 1: Pictorial representation of Flexible floor diaphragm as per IS 1893:2016

Literature Review

Asymmetric constructions are unavoidable owing to design considerations, yet due to plan irregularity, they are more susceptible to seismic damage than symmetric structures. In such asymmetrical constructions, shear walls are advised to lessen the lateral stress on the columns [2]. To support new recommendations, the appropriate seismic analysis for asymmetrical structures is researched. For different asymmetrical plan forms, including the L and W shape, equivalent static analysis, response spectrum analysis, and time history analysis were performed. It is discovered that time history analysis produces deflection values far greater than the permissible limit, equivalent static analysis produces deflection values that are within the permissible limit. Even if it produces deflection values that are lower than those of time history analysis, equivalent static method does not meet the deflection condition [4]. Seismic analysis is done in Staad Pro, Etabs, and SAP 2000 to examine the effects of seismic parameters in irregular buildings. For irregular constructions that are taller than 40m, it is advised to use dynamic analysis [3]. For the purpose of analysing the seismic requirements of irregular structures, both linear and non-linear analysis is used. It has been noted that pushover static analysis produces unfavourable results for the vertical distribution of lateral force while similar static analysis ignores irregular effects and produces abnormal results [1]. Diaphragm discontinuities, such as variations in slab thickness or slab opening, are regarded as a type of mass irregularity that affects the structure's stiffness. [5] In this study, Etabs is used to simulate rectangular-plan structures with various opening percentages. Force and displacement are inversely correlated in models of mass irregularity. Because of increase in shear force, displacement is high for irregular models relative to regular models, leading to decrease in the performance of the structure during earthquakes. [6] Response spectrum analysis is used to examine the impact of slab openings at various positions, including the center, corner, and peripheral locations, with various column shapes, including rectangular and square. With an increase in the percentage of opening area, the base shear increases. Slab opening in the middle is determined to be more efficient when looking at base shear, displacement, and drift. [7] For a structure having slab opening at the center, corner, and periphery, the equivalent static analysis and pushover analysis are performed. Slab opening at the peripheral case is observed to be crucial. The difference between static and pushover analysis is 7%.

Objectives

1. To study seismic effects on asymmetric plan shape (T and L shape)
2. To create several diaphragm openings for the purpose of studying the structure's seismic response.
3. To take into account the various degrees of diaphragm flexibility under the seismic activity.
4. To evaluate the seismic response characteristics like as base shear, displacement, and interstorey drift by utilizing response spectrum analysis method in the Etabs program.
5. To study the elemental forces due under the influence of diaphragm flexibility.

Building Properties and Model

Table 1: Material properties and loading conditions

No of Story	G+5
Story Height	3.5 m
Number of Bays and width	6 bays in both directions of 6 m x 3.5 m
Grade of Concrete	M 30
Grade of Steel	Fe 415
Beam Size and column size	200 mm x 400 mm and 400 mm x 400 mm
Live load	3 kN/m ²
Roof live load	1.5 kN/m ²
Floor finish	1 kN/m ²
Seismic Zone	III

Response reduction factor	5
Importance factor	1
Soil type	Medium

Table 2: Model details

Plan shape	Model name	Plan dimensions	No. of bays in the direction of		Bay width in direction of		Size of opening	% Of opening
			X	Y	X	Y		
T shape	T	42mx27m	7	6	6m	4.5m	-	-
	T1	42mx27m	7	6	6m	4.5m	1 no. of 3mx3m	1.5%
	T2	42mx27m	7	6	6m	4.5m	3 no. of 2mx2m	1.5%
L shape	L	36mx27m	6	6	6m	4.5m	-	-
	L1	36mx27m	6	6	6m	4.5m	1 no. of 3mx3m	2%
	L2	36mx27m	6	6	6m	4.5m	3 no. of 2mx2m	2%

Table 3: Position of openings

T shape	Centre Opening		Corner opening	
L shape	Centre Opening		Corner opening	

Results and Discussions

Base Shear

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2 (a): Base shear in X direction; (b): Base shear in Y direction

In both X and Y direction, the base shear of both T shape and L shape is observed to be minimum for the Centre opening case. Base shear decreases with increase in diaphragm flexibility. L shape is found to be crucial under seismic response.

Maximum Story displacement

In both the direction, highest maximum displacement is found to be at centre opening in T shape and at corner opening in L shape. Maximum story displacement increases with increase in flexibility. T shape shows the highest displacement value compared to the L shape.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3(a): Max. story displacement in X direction; (b): Max. story displacement in Y direction

Story drift

T shape with centre opening has significantly high story drift in both rigid and flexible diaphragms. In L shape, corner opening yields high story drift. Similar to story displacement, story drift also increases with increase in diaphragm flexibility. The T shape is more crucial than L shape with significant difference in story drift.

Axial force

Axial force is more in T shape compared to L shape in no opening and center opening case. In corner opening case, axial force in L shape is slightly higher than the T shape. Axial force is least affected by the diaphragm flexibility.

Shear force

Shear force is maximum for center opening in T shape and corner opening case for L shape. With increase in diaphragm flexibility, shear force decreases.

(a)

(b)

Fig.4 (a): Story drift in X direction; (b) Story drift in Y direction

Fig. 5: Axial force in column

Fig. 6: Shear force in beam

Bending Moment

Fig. 7: Bending moment in beam

Bending moment is maximum for centre opening in T shape and corner opening case for L shape. The bending moment values of 25% flexible diaphragm is lower than both rigid and 25% flexible diaphragm.

Conclusion

Seismic response parameters were investigated for rigid diaphragm and flexible diaphragm with 25% and 50% flexibility no opening, a centre opening, a corner opening cases of T and L shape. The results are quantitatively expressed as follows:

1. In T shape, in both the directions, base shear decreases by 6% in the centre opening case whereas it increases by 11.5% in the corner opening case compared to the no opening case. In L shape, the base shear decreases by 1% in both the directions for centre opening case whereas it increases by 11% in X direction and 8% in Y direction for corner opening case.
2. Maximum story displacement in T shape, in both directions, shows an increase of 43% in centre and 11% in corner opening respectively. In L shape, centre opening has insignificant increase whereas corner opening shows 11% increase in X direction and 32% increase in Y direction.
3. Story drift of T shape plan with centre opening shows an increment of 1.45 times the no opening case in both X and Y direction. In T shape with corner opening, an increase of 7% story drift value is observed. There is no difference in the story drift value in L shape with centre opening whereas corner opening has 11.5% increase in X direction and 32% increase in Y direction respectively.
4. Neither the different levels of flexibility nor the openings influence the axial force in T shape plan. In L shape plan, only the corner opening case shows hike of 58% increase in axial force compared to no opening case.

5. Shear force and bending moment decreases in case of corner opening case in both the plan shapes. No change in shear force and bending moment is observed in centre opening case of L shape.

References

1. Ravikumar, C. M., Babu Narayan, K. S., Sujith, B. V., & Venkat Reddy, D. (2012), "Effect of irregular configurations on seismic vulnerability of RC buildings", *Architecture Research*, 2:20-26.
2. Pokharel, S., Ganesh, S. L., & Sabarish, G. (2019), "Seismic performance of symmetric and asymmetric multi-storeyed buildings", *Int J Recent Technol Eng*, 8:364-369.
3. Firoj, M., & Singh, S. K. (2018), "Response spectrum analysis for irregular multi-storey structure in seismic zone V", In 16th Symposium on Earthquake Engineering, IIT Roorkee, India, 1-9.
4. Bagawan, R. K., & Patel, M. Q. (2017), "Seismic Performance Study of RC Framed building with Diaphragm Discontinuity".
5. Manmathan, A. V., & Aiswarya, S. (2017), "Analysis of buildings with varying percentages of diaphragm openings", *IJERT*, 6:461-466.
6. Baby, B. E., & Sreeja, S. (2016), "Analysis of buildings with slab discontinuity", *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 5.
7. Doudoumis, I. N., & Athanatopoulou, A. M. (2001), "Code provisions and analytical modelling for the in-plane flexibility of floor diaphragms in building structures", *Journal of earthquake engineering*, 5: 565-594.
8. Moeini, M., & Rafezy, B. (2011), "Investigation into the floor diaphragms flexibility in reinforced concrete structures and code provision", *Global Journal of Researches in Engineering*, 11:25-35.
9. Herbudiman, B., Pribadi, A., & Ayu, V. K. (2020), "Rigid, Semi Rigid, and Flexible Diaphragms for Horizontally Asymmetric Building", In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON GREEN TECHNOLOGY AND DESIGN (ICGTD)*, 2020:41-45.
10. Bahar, S., Benanane, A., & BELARBI, A. (2019), "The influence of deformability of horizontal diaphragms in the distribution of seismic loads to bracing elements in rectangular buildings", *Journal of Materials and Engineering Structures*, JMES, 6, 105-118.
11. Eivani, H., S Moghadam, A., Aziminejad, A., & Nekooei, M. (2018), "Effects of diaphragm flexibility on seismic response of asymmetric-plan buildings", *Grđevinar*, 70:965-974.
12. Akshay Nagpure, S. S. Sanghai, 2018, "Effect of Diaphragm Flexibility on the Seismic Response of RCC Framed Building Considering Diaphragm Discontinuity", *International Journal of Innovations in Engineering and Science*, 3:2456-3463
13. Basu, D., & Jain, S. K. (2004), "Seismic analysis of asymmetric buildings with flexible floor diaphragms", *Journal of structural engineering*, 130: 1169-1176.